

СОЦИО-КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ КОМПОНЕНТЫ В УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛАХ ПО АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPONENTS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING MATERIALS

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Abstract

The article deals with the process of paying special attention to the cultural realities in the English language teaching materials. The English language educational materials developers have tried to expand the system of socio-cultural knowledge offered to users. At the same time, the growing focus on the English language recognizes its significant contribution to English-speaking culture and also contributes to the general democratization of the knowledge we can acquire from teaching materials.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается процесс уделения особого внимания культурным реалиям в учебных материалах по английскому языку. Разработчики англоязычных учебных материалов постарались расширить систему социокультурных знаний, предлагаемых пользователям. В то же время растущее внимание к английскому языку признает его значительный вклад в англоязычную культуру, а также способствует общей демократизации знаний, которые мы можем получить из учебных материалов.

Ключевые слова: социо-культурные компоненты, учебные материалы, английский язык, изучающие иностранный язык, связь, реалии.

Keywords: socio-cultural components, teaching materials, the English language, foreign language learners, connection, realities.

An important feature of English educational complexes is that those who have a relatively low level of language skills receive explanations in the teaching materials, accompanied by examples from the life of the country and the people. At this stage of the training, attention is paid to some social problems: unemployment, youth employment, migration, etc. It should be noted that this series of textbooks is intended for young people and adults over 16 years of age, but in practice, these teaching materials are sometimes used by young audiences.

It is necessary to pay attention to the characteristics of the sociocultural topics and problems chosen by the authors for presentation. After analysing many of these materials, it is possible to note their constant pragmatic orientation, focusing on practical problems in the lives of modern people. This applies to many generations: from schoolchildren to the elderly, some texts are devoted to the problems of the older generation, their position in society [3].

Speaking about the ways of representation of the sociocultural component in educational complexes, we can note that different models are preferred depending on the level of language proficiency. For example, at the primary level, these are either very small texts of three or four sentences, or daily dialogues on socio-cultural topics of education and leisure. Starting at the intermediate level, each subsequent step is preceded by longer texts on a specific socio-cultural problem, fol-

lowed by a discussion using a list of questions to formulate your point of view or suggest solutions to the problem.

We can see it in socio-cultural materials related to the English language and often in texts on socio-cultural issues. The most diverse grammatical topics and structures (how to formulate advice, express desires or criticize) are worked out precisely on socio-cultural material. This is how the concept of modern teaching materials in English is built. "It can be argued that the socio-cultural component in modern English teaching materials is the basis of the approach to teaching in the true sense of the word" [1].

Teaching materials in English as a foreign language are extremely rich in socio-cultural components, and each individual lesson has socio-cultural information, many tasks on socio-cultural problems, separate sections and teaching materials dedicated to it. Almost every section of the course devoted to socio-cultural issues, for example, the section on education and school system, ends with questions related to the topic under consideration.

English language teaching materials as a foreign language at all levels also include issues of ecology and environmental protection. This issue has become especially relevant in the last decade due to environmental pollution and increasing population density in many countries. Every year in modern English educational complexes, the authors pay more attention to the problems of ecology and climate change. The discussion of

these problems is given more and more space in the socio-cultural component.

The project description states that parcels that should not be disposed with household waste are marked with a special green sticker and collected in separate bags for recycling. Also, glass, paper, old clothes, biological waste and "special" waste that do not belong to any of the defined categories are collected separately from other waste.

Audio materials on socio-cultural issues of environmental protection are mostly interviews on the streets of English-speaking countries, where people are asked about their attitude to the need to protect the environment and their contribution to this activity. We learn that people's attitudes to environmental issues are not so ambiguous, and some are annoyed by the fact that this topic is so relevant and often mentioned in the media: "I already have three trash cans in my small kitchen – it's just crazy!" As always, you can hear another version of the approach to the problem: "Why are aluminium cans not banned? Our children will never drink canned lemonade" [5].

Given the great and growing attention paid to this topic in modern educational complexes, it can be concluded that the formation of environmental awareness has become an important part of the cultural policy of all countries, which is reflected in the common cultural origins of states and their inhabitants.

Another very interesting and indicator that can be observed in the latest training kits, is the trend in the selection of socio-cultural material. About English as a foreign language offered by major publishers: reading and listening materials are becoming more widespread. Such texts are accompanied by comments and colour illustrations. When analysing such texts, we encounter several important points in terms of socio-cultural content, and we see that they differ from the situation in modern Western European culture in comparison with our country.

The immigrant groups also attract the attention of the authors of English teaching materials. Take, for example, the hearing on the problems of international relations in Europe. Italian workers in Germany complain of harassment (hide their tools, name them, make fun of them). The Greek woman is concerned that German employers want to hire only locals and migrants only for low wages. This socio-cultural theme is increasingly represented in modern European educational complexes after the development of a multicultural European society.

The purpose of English language teaching materials is to interest students, to arouse a clear and unchanging interest in the culture of the country where the language is studied. Achieving this goal is also facilitated by students presenting grammatical material that is traditionally considered boring and difficult to master.

In modern English teaching materials, grammar is almost never presented in the form of systematic rules. It is presented almost exclusively on the basis of situational models. Since the "simple to complex" rule is still followed and every proposed situation is followed, we can talk about a system of certain situations that

constitute the description of English grammar as a foreign language in English-language teaching complexes.

Although there is no known sequence in the presentation of grammar mentioned by many teachers, a workbook has been added to the textbooks. Such workbooks use not only many additional tasks for translation and grammar exercises, but also a system-theoretical description of grammar in the form of tables, which are traditional for these textbooks.

This functional-communicative approach is most common in modern English-language teaching materials. Because it allows students to more effectively explain what usually causes them the greatest practical difficulties. The endings can be memorized immediately, but this does not answer the key question of usage, and students quickly acquire skills by relying on situations and multiple dialogues, including socio-cultural dialogues." It is important that the dialogues include a consistent set of greetings and examples of reactions to everyday questions" [4].

Continuing to study the socio-cultural components of English as a foreign language in English educational kits, we can mention another topic of social and cultural significance that is found in most modern teaching materials. This is the topic of "Elderly" or "Care for the Elderly", which is sometimes covered under the general theme of "Family" and sometimes as an independent chapter.

For example - Nursing Home, Grandparents, Community Service, Helping the Needy, Occupations Related to Caring for the Sick or Elderly, Spending Time With the Family, Helping Children With School Assignments, Interfering With Family Life, Being Important to Children, Playing With Children, Having Enough Space at Home, Problems Arising, Not Being Alone, Getting Sick, Leading an Active Lifestyle, Being Healthy, Arguing, Being Able to Continue Working, Feeling Young etc [4].

We can observe the formation of social problems within this sociocultural theme, which is typical for teaching materials on foreign languages in the west in general. For example, the lesson opens by presenting a number of specific people's perspectives on whether or not to send elderly grandparents to a nursing home.

The introductory text offers at least three different perspectives on the question raised, as well as an older person's comment. A few sentences that reflect the suggested ideas It can be said that the coexistence of different generations between many sections of socio-cultural problems and the problems of older people are gaining more and more attention in the teaching materials. Undoubtedly, the socio-economic situation in the country (aging population, pension expenditures, maintenance of nursing homes and social benefits for the elderly) is growing. Such socio-cultural issues and related problems are becoming increasingly relevant for developed European countries.

According to the logic of English-language teaching materials, after getting acquainted with the views expressed on the subject, users of teaching materials are always invited to comment on the proposed positions and ultimately to form their own opinions. The main

thing that stimulates English-language teaching materials with a wide application of the problem approach and almost constant problem relations is to form, express and substantiate their point of view. From a linguistic and cultural point of view, the ability to articulate one's point of view in a discussion plays a special role, which is to target most tasks using sociocultural problems.

This approach to the presentation of sociocultural material increases the interest in the topic. It allows not only to get acquainted with the information, but also to form their own views on sociocultural problems, to express their views on issues of social importance. This is facilitated by creative tasks and projects, such as holding round tables and conferences on socio-cultural issues, a portfolio - a kind of sociocultural portrait of the target country. As possible topics of the assignments, it is suggested to compile a map of the country showing the geographical landscapes, political or economic zoning of the settlements of different peoples.

Another question is related to family socio-cultural topics, which are often found in modern teaching materials. For example: "When can a child go on vacation alone?" Topics such as are offered as an independent topic of discussion.

Listening assignments often ask the listener to link the question to the expert's answer and then comment on the answers based on the suggested guide list. There is a clash of opinions of teenagers, parents and young people. As an example, let's take a classic story: a 21-year-old girl complains to the psychologist-host of a radio program that her parents always want them to go to the same place on vacation every year. She wants to go to another country with a friend. The psychologist suggested: "Your parents can't forbid you because you are an adult." Assignment: "Do you agree with the psychologist's answer? At what age do young people in your country become independent?" [2].

Cultural diversification is always observed at the level of differentiation of relevant preferences of boys and girls in the development of topics related to leisure, hobbies and the choice of preferred professions. These lessons are mainly devoted to basic vocabulary and grammar, but already within this low level of language skills they provide a significant amount of socio-cultural information about various aspects of a teenager's life. Almost any sociocultural material, as well as control over the mastery of this material, ends with a reference to the native culture of students: "Speak about your country!"

This is of particular interest to students, as it allows them to compare the learned sociocultural realities with their own realities, to identify differences, to think about the reasons for these differences, which is especially interesting for adolescents. When students talk

with interest about the social and cultural differences between what they are learning and what they are getting used to, their overall motivation to master the foreign language they are learning and the culture behind it increases. The sociocultural component undoubtedly provides methodological support to teachers in order to arouse students' interest in the subject and encourage them to learn more about language and culture.

If we talk about the criteria for selecting socio-cultural and linguistic material for representation in English language teaching materials, it seems that the relevance of the considered socio-cultural situations and problems, their final connection with the realities of everyday life plays a key role. At the same time, attention is paid to different segments of society and generations, which can be called a special advantage of English language teaching materials.

They provide their users with a fairly complete picture of the country's home culture and provide detailed information about how their citizens live and what they think, and what problems they face. It should be added that questions about the history and spiritual culture of the country began to play a significant role in modern educational materials. Their pragmatic orientation in terms of structure and content is increasingly expressed.

More attention is paid to the current situation in the country and the changes in the lives of its residents. Changes in society, politics, economy, and culture are coming to the fore, and there is a desire to make teaching materials extremely relevant in terms of the target language country today. These changes, in recent years, have been devoted by educational publishers to most of the socio-cultural materials in modern English-language teaching complexes as a foreign language.

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